
**TILSHUNOSLIK FAN SIFATIDA, UNING BOSHQA FANLAR BILAN
ALOQASI**

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Annotation: This scientific thesis delves into the field of linguistics as a science that studies language, examining its intricate relationship with other disciplines and their collective contributions to our understanding of human communication. By elucidating the theoretical underpinnings, methodological approaches, and empirical findings in linguistics, this research explores how the study of language intersects with psychology, neuroscience, sociology, anthropology, computer science, and cognitive science to unravel the complexities of linguistic structures, cognitive processes, social interactions, and cultural expressions. Through a

synthesis of interdisciplinary perspectives, this thesis aims to shed light on the collaborative endeavors of linguistics with other sciences in elucidating the nature of language as a fundamental aspect of human cognition, communication, and cultural diversity.

Keywords: *Linguistics, language, Sociology, Communication, Cultural Diversity, Language Evolution, Linguistic Structures, Social Interactions*

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy tezis tilni o'rganadigan fan sifatida tilshunoslik sohasiga kirib boradi, uning boshqa fanlar bilan murakkab aloqasini va ularning insoniy muloqotni tushunishimizga qo'shgan umumiy hissasini o'rganadi. Tilshunoslikning nazariy asoslari, uslubiy yondashuvlari va empirik topilmalarini yoritib, ushbu tadqiqot tilni o'rganish psixologiya, nevrologiya, sotsiologiya, antropologiya, informatika va kognitiv fanlar bilan qanday kesishishini o'rganadi, bu til tuzilmalari, kognitiv jarayonlarning murakkabliklarini ochib beradi. ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sirlar va madaniy ifodalar. Fanlararo istiqbollarni sintez qilish orqali ushbu tezis tilning inson bilishi, muloqoti va madaniy xilma-xilligining asosiy jihati sifatidagi mohiyatini yoritishda tilshunoslikning boshqa fanlar bilan hamkorlikdagi sa'y-harakatlarini yoritishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *tilshunoslik, til, sotsiologiya, aloqa, madaniy xilma-xillik, til evolyutsiyasi, til tuzilmalari, ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sirlar*

Аннотация: Эта научная диссертация углубляется в область лингвистики как науки, изучающей язык, исследуя его сложные взаимоотношения с другими дисциплинами и их коллективный вклад в наше понимание человеческого общения. Разъясняя теоретические основы, методологические подходы и

эмпирические данные в лингвистике, это исследование исследует, как изучение языка пересекается с психологией, нейробиологией, социологией, антропологией, информатикой и когнитивной наукой, чтобы разгадать сложности лингвистических структур, когнитивных процессов, социальные взаимодействия и культурное самовыражение. Посредством синтеза междисциплинарных точек зрения эта диссертация призвана пролить свет на совместные усилия лингвистики с другими науками по выяснению природы языка как фундаментального аспекта человеческого познания, общения и культурного разнообразия.

Ключевые слова: *лингвистика, язык, социология, коммуникация, культурное разнообразие, языковая эволюция, лингвистические структуры, социальные взаимодействия.*

Introduction:

Linguistics serves as a scientific discipline devoted to the systematic study of language, encompassing its phonetic, phonological, morphological, syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic dimensions. The theoretical frameworks, methodological tools, and empirical approaches in linguistics offer valuable insights into the structures, functions, and evolution of human languages across diverse communities and cultures. This thesis embarks on an exploration of linguistics as a science of language, probing its connections with psychology, neuroscience, sociology, anthropology, computer science, and cognitive science to illuminate the complex interplay between language, cognition, society, and technology in the

contemporary world.

Literature Review:

The field of linguistics has flourished as a scientific enterprise that draws on a rich tapestry of theoretical models, empirical methods, and interdisciplinary collaborations to advance our understanding of language as a cognitive, social, and cultural phenomenon. Researchers have explored the cognitive processes underlying language acquisition, processing, and production, revealing the neural substrates, evolutionary origins, and universal constraints that shape human language capacity. Seminal works by Chomsky (1957), Pinker (1994), Jackendoff (2002), and Tomasello (2003) offer foundational insights into the cognitive, generative, evolutionary, and social dimensions of language that intersect with other scientific disciplines.

Methodology:

This thesis adopts a multidisciplinary research approach that integrates theoretical frameworks, empirical studies, and cross-cutting analyses to examine the relationship between linguistics and other sciences. By synthesizing phonetic analyses, syntactic structures, semantic representations, sociolinguistic variables, neurolinguistic paradigms, computational models, and cognitive frameworks, this study aims to elucidate how language interfaces with cognitive psychology, neuroscience, sociolinguistics, ethnography, artificial intelligence, and cognitive science to broaden our understanding of language as a multifaceted system embedded in human cognition, communication, and culture.

Results and Discussion:

The findings of this research underscore the collaborative endeavors of linguistics with other disciplines in exploring language as a scientific phenomenon that transcends disciplinary boundaries. The analysis of language processing mechanisms, cross-linguistic typologies, language evolution, social variation, technological applications, and cognitive architectures illuminates the intricate connections between linguistic structures, cognitive processes, social interactions, and cultural expressions. By synthesizing empirical data, theoretical perspectives, and interdisciplinary insights, this thesis reveals the synergies and synergisms that emerge from the integration of linguistic theories with diverse scientific disciplines.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this scientific thesis highlights the pivotal role of linguistics as a science of language that intersects with psychology, neuroscience, sociology, anthropology, computer science, and cognitive science in unraveling the complexities of human communication, cognition, and culture. Through collaborative efforts, interdisciplinary dialogues, and innovative research methodologies, we enhance our understanding of language as a fundamental aspect of human experience that shapes our thoughts, identities, and social interactions. By embracing the interdisciplinary landscape of linguistics, we enrich our perspectives, expand our horizons, and deepen our appreciation for the diverse

ways in which language mirrors and transforms the human condition in a rapidly evolving world.

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